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INVESTIGATION ON DESIGN METHOD AND THINKING OF CHAIN REACTION GAME FOR IMAGE-BASED PROBLEM-SOLVING ABILITY

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ABSTRACT

This study refers to the components of chain reactions assembly as the design concept for designing interactive games. The whole process of chain reaction consists of various scientific components such as gear devices and tool modules. The purpose of this study is to use the procedures in the CPS model (Creative Problem Solving) as the analytical model by Parnes (1967) in order to identify the game design method and comprehend the ability of users in solving image-based problem based on visual information in the whole process of game operation. The research results hope to explore the cognitive processes in image-based problem-solving ability, and can assist the designers to consider the design thinking of interactive games and strengthen problem-solving abilities.

Keywords: chain reaction, game design method, design thinking, problem-solving ability

INTRODUCTION

LEGO is a well-known and fascinating toy, and presents component assembly structure. The basic functions are various types of small components, and the game techniques of connections, juxtaposition, stacking, arrangement, and combinations, and other operational rules and models are used to form specific structures. The points of interest are: the correlation between perception responses to the assembly and operational processes of LEGO models, and how image signals in the design process influence the thinking and problem-solving cognitive behavior of designers. Many studies have pointed out that, interactive games can strengthen the cognitive concepts of problem-solving procedures.

Incorporating story scenarios, interesting, challenging, and novel characteristics in the process of design to guide players in understanding the problem and in motivating exploration, would positively help the elevation of problem-solving abilities. This is closely related to the evolution of creative thinking.

In sci-fi films, the plots similar to the LEGO-based concept are frequently seen and audiences tend to find them novel and interesting. In the sci-fi film "Back to the Future," the mad and talented doctor who invented "time machine" exhibited his creativity in various aspects of life. The doctor was fond of invention and invented a series of machinery devices. As long as the starter gear is successfully operated, the "chain reaction" of machines could further complete the predetermined objectives. For example, the doctor designed a machine which could cook a simple dish "egg and toast." When he turned on the starter, the chain reaction of machine would be automatically triggered. During the reaction, the egg would be whisked, pan-fried, and seasoned, the toast would be baked, and the food would be dished up. The reactions originally had to be completed by manpower were completed by the machine. During the reaction of the machine, predetermined starting point and endpoint were established for each mechanical unit. The endpoint of one mechanical unit was the starting point of the next one. The entire process was full of interesting changes, which also implied a certain extent of humor.

This study refers to the components of chain reaction assembly (LEGO-based components) as the design concept for designing interactive games. The game concept uses the tools and components for assembly of different gears as the operational rules, while the key point of the problem is to activate chain

reactions formed by various scientific components, to guide users in choosing the correct and suitable trigger tools to construct gear devices with continuous motivation, and finally achieve the game objective of solving the problem. The design concept of the scientific device primarily refers to the nature and life sciences subjects in Taiwanese elementary schools: it covers the lecture content of “force”, “sunlight”, “air”, “three states of water”, “temperature”, “plants”, and “electricity and magnetism,” which are used as developmental concepts of the game scenario script for chain reactions.

The purpose of this study is to use the procedures in the CPS model (Creative Problem Solving) as the analytical model by Parnes (1967): FF (Fact Finding), PF (Problem Finding), IF (Idea Finding), SF (Solution Finding), and AF (Acceptance Finding), in order to identify the design method and discuss the design thinking concepts and visual design factors to be focused on during various stages of game design. Game operation explores the ability of users in solving image-based problem based on visual signals. The chain reaction-style problems are solved in this way, and users are observed in terms of cognitive responses to the operational signals provided by the game before perceiving the problem. Furthermore, this study evaluates how the signal content guides users to discover the key problem and its features in the process of the game, and how they explore and evaluate solution strategies.

As for the research procedures, after brainstorming method was used to design the scenario scripts of four game scenario scripts, the content design, interface design, and interactive design of the games were conducted to complete the eventual game prototype of chain reaction. Moreover, CPS analysis model was used to investigate the design thinking for interactive procedure of game operation.

CREATIVE THINKING AND PROBLEM SOLVING

The nature of creativity has constantly been investigated. Rhodes (1961) proposed 4P (Person, Process, Product, and Press) from the “problem-oriented” perspective, in order to explain the intrinsic characteristics and nature of creativity: personality traits, creative process, creative output, and interaction between creative individuals and

environment. It is generally accepted that creativity is a comprehensive ability, including the comprehensive performance combining mind with personality traits such as the ability to create novel things, the ability to create problem-solving process, the thinking ability to analyze matters, and the ability to connect and transform existing things into new changes. Moreover, relevant studies indicated that games could help enhance creative learning. Sylva et al. (1976) found in the study on children that game process could increase children’s behavioral choice and improve their problem-solving. Moreover, it was also beneficial to divergent thinking ability and insight ability (Vandenberg, 1980; Dansky, 1980). Moreover, in addition to learning problem-solving method, it also directly triggered creative thinking to develop more strategies and methods for problem-solving (Pepler & Ross, 1981).

The studies on the effect of interactive games on game players’ creative performance investigated how players identified clues such as relevant information and sensory perception to further identify, analyze, and solve problems during game process. In addition, such studies also investigated how individuals exhibited comprehensive thinking, as well as characteristics and ability of in-depth exploration, and how they simplified problems and developed various problem-solving methods flexibly. The hypothesis of such studies is that games can trigger players’ positive motivation and interest in further exploration on the themes, and interactive model can create more user-friendly operating environment to satisfy players’ need for responding to various scenarios during the exploration process. Although the game contents may be predetermined and planned in advance passively, players can actively determine their roles and status to achieve the positive effect of creative performance. The challenging learning scenario of interactive games is beneficial to users’ creative performance (Amabile, 1996; Sternberg, 2005). In addition, game-based learning has a positive effect on learning motivation, learning cognition, and learning effectiveness. Some scholars suggested that games could facilitate the learning of participants (Prensky, 2001; Gee, 2005). There are several game features during teaching process (Rubin, Fein & Vandenberg, 1983): (1) Games are referral activities and are

different from daily living experiences because there are fixed behavioral patterns and it is hard to simply distinguish it based on external behaviors. (2) Games are the behaviors derived from intrinsic motivation, and motivation may be changed by the stimuli of external environment. (3) Although the results of game playing can affect players' sense of accomplishment, the process is sometimes more important than the result. Therefore, teaching activities are flexible and unrestrained and may vary with the change in game courses. (4) Games are usually joyful. The difference between games and the concept of exploration is that games are more "self-referenced," while exploration is more object-referenced.

The value of problem-solving is not only the operational results, but the process (Gagne et al., 1993). Some studies suggested that problem-solving is an explicit or cognitive behavioral process where various potential effective solutions are proposed in the attempt to respond to the problem scenario, and more effective one is chosen to be implemented (Polya, 1981). It is generally accepted that problem-solving is the thinking process for problems. The psychological processes of problem-solving are generalized into discovery of the existence of the problem, understanding of the nature of the problem, collection of relevant information, action to solve the problem, and after-action review and assessment. A "problem" is the difference between objective and current status, and problem solving is the process where individuals use the knowledge and skill they have learnt to meet the need of a specific situation and to further obtain a solution.

Games can help strengthen the awareness of problems and scenarios (Mayer, 2002). The integration of scenarios during design process can trigger players' understanding of problems and exploration motivation, which has a positive effect on improving players' problem-solving ability. In addition to game learning, Parnes (1967) suggested that the complicated process of "Creative problem solving (CPS)" is the integration of two fields, creative thinking and problem solving. In CPS, problems are solved mainly based on systemic thinking. Before the solution is developed and the decision is implemented, more diversified potential

methods can be proposed for evaluation. The stages of the process include:

- Stage of Fact Finding (FF): to look for more clues and information from the current status.
- Stage of Problem Finding (PF): to clarify the problem in order to obtain the problems or concept that can be explicitly described.
- Stage of Idea Finding (IF): to further obtain various ideas about the problem, including trying and exploration.
- Stage of Solution Finding (SF): to obtain the rules for evaluating the advantages/disadvantages of various ideas and to choose the most appropriate one as the solution.
- Stage of Acceptance Finding (AF): to repeatedly explore the solution to the problem systemically, and another solution or the final approach may be obtained.

CPS model may not be implemented completely in a certain order. Howe (1997) suggested that each stage of CPS may occur independently and may even intertwine with each other nonlinearly. Each stage includes convergent thinking and divergent thinking. CPS is usually initiated from divergent thinking and terminated with convergent thinking to assess and clarify the practicability of solution. In addition, the entire process is on a periodic basis. Csikszentmihalyi (1996) indicated that the addition of entertaining, playful, and joyful incentives to game design of game scenarios can attract participants to participate in games to explore and accept challenging tasks. Players can achieve objectives by developing problem-solving strategies and obtain satisfaction and sense of accomplishment during the process of problem-solving. When a certain kind of balance between the challenge of game tasks and skill of players is reached, such experiences enable participants to enter the Flow stage of game playfulness and participants will feel interested in the surroundings unconsciously and exhibit creativity.

INTERFACE DESIGN AND DESIGN METHOD FOR CHAIN REACTION GAME

CONCEPT FOR SCENARIO DESIGN

This study designed four game scenarios: Risk Precaution, Obstacle Eliminations, Situation Balances, and Confident Challenges. This study mainly used brainstorming method to develop chain reaction game scenarios for the course of nature science and life technology of elementary schools in Taiwan. A complete story plot included three structures, beginning, development, and ending, in order to convey the meaning hidden in the plot. The plot could be described in a humorous way to enable users to become aware of scenarios easily. During the game process, creative plots could be used to trigger the users' awareness of the problem and the design of chain reactions in the teaching content of nature science and life technology enabled users to obtain abundant plots. For example, "pouring a glass of water" would result in the phenomenon of "water gradually overflowing." However, the phenomenon of water overflowing was not the result of final appeal, but the starter to trigger the next chain reaction. Similarly, the result of the next chain reaction would become the initial catalyst of following one. The four different scenario scripts had their own appeals. The appeal of the first one, Risk Precaution, was to solve the disaster going to occur in the game scenario. Users had to be aware of the signs of disasters and thought about the problem-solving strategy to prevent a disaster from happening. For example, the foresaid phenomenon of water overflowing caused by pouring a glass of water was intended for putting out a fire gradually spreading around to achieve the purpose of preventing disasters from occurring. The appeal of the second one, Obstacle Eliminations was to solve the predicaments faced by the role designed in the game. For example, if the game roles had to get away from or get close to the object around them, users had to try to pass on the object to get away from or get close to the location where the role was at. The appeal of the third one, Situation Balances, was to assess the status of the existence of various situations at different ratios in a game, which obviously led to unexpected results. The process of balancing the overall situation could help

successfully achieve the predetermined objective, and such an objective usually possessed positive educational meaning. For example, users could learn to balance the currently unstable situation under time pressure. The appeal of the fourth one, Confident Challenges, was to break through the record of the game role. The performance ability was the prototype of the scenario. The chain reaction process could strengthen the confidence of game role and improve the behavioral ability to overcome challenges.

GAME INTERFACE DESIGN

This study developed the problem-solving game prototype of chain reaction. The visual style of mechanical experimental components was used in the game interface design. The design concept triggered users' willingness to explore the game and the main objective was to intrigue users' operational interest, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Problem-solving game prototype of chain reaction.

As for the game screen, the copper tube circuits around the screen constituted a closed circuit device. The interface included four components, electronic cabinet menu, mouse power switch, tool hanging boards, and game scenario area of chain reaction. The functions of the electronic cabinet menu included master switch, game topics, and brief introduction to tool module function. The design of cute, interesting, and anthropomorphic mouse was applied to the mouse power switch. The mouse stood

on a switch gear where the originally predetermined state was “broken circuit.” The mouse held one wire terminal in the right and left hands, respectively. When the state was switched to “unobstructed circuit,” the right and left hands of the mouse would be connected with circuit terminals to complete the electric conduction. The process of electric conduction was exhibited in a humorous way. After the device was powered up, the gear wheel device was energized and thus rolled.

Tool hanging boards were designed as the area to place all the gear wheel components and tool modules. All the tool parts (as specified in Appendix) were placed on different pages. For the use of tool parts, the tool parts should be dragged to the game scenario area of chain reaction. For the disposal, the tool parts should be dragged to the recycling device of scenario area. The game scenario area was the animation area of game task, clue to problem, and presentation of chain reaction.

DESIGN THINKING FOR OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES OF CHAIN REACTION GAME

DESIGN THINKING IN CHAIN REACTION CONCEPT

In the procedure of chain reaction, every component could be viewed as the following three roles, and shown in Figure 2:

- **Beginning:** It referred to the beginning of the chain reaction procedure and was usually the source of mechanical power (power device), such as power switch, battery, wind power, and any relevant objects that could generate power.
- **Intermediate:** Its function was to convey power. Mechanical tools such as gear wheel components, conveyor belts, pendant cord, and ring-pull all played the intermediate role in the entire chain reaction procedure. Most of the key points of the predetermined problems of scenario scripts were not intermediate roles. In addition, they usually guided users to develop models which could solve problems through the visual clue of intermediate. They usually gave users a hint to operate the components of chain reaction to achieve the purpose of game task, namely, to trigger the interface and condition of chain reaction components.

- **Termination:** It received the power change conveyed by the intermediate to trigger the correct chain reaction, as well as the efficacy activated by chain reaction components. When users explore the possible method to solve problems, termination (endpoint) is usually the role animation implied by predetermined scenario. In addition, its spatial correlation with the role was also higher. Because such a role was fictional and simulated, it could guide users in fulfilling their imagination and arouse their interest to trigger the operation of various chain reaction components.

Figure 2. Explanation about response operation of chain reaction device.

If each component could possess the functions of the three roles above, users could constitute and construct numerous chain reaction procedures at their will. Because they could freely arrange the devices, various operational possibilities were available and thus the level of difficulty of challenges was decreased. The analysis on the details of chain reaction procedures indicated that, a basic component could be regarded as the beginning, as well as the termination of the previous procedure. The termination was also the beginning of the next procedure. The intermediate played the role to convey power, instead of the key point to the scenario problem (as shown in Figure 2). In order to guide users in systemically observing possible problem-solving model and solution, identifying problems, deconstructing problems, and describing how to solve problems, it was necessary to strengthen the explanation about the relationship between termination and key points of scenario problems, as well as to establish various beginning components for users to think about the assembly model of possible solutions. The use of interesting components could further trigger various chain reaction procedures. The basic

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the correlation between motivate power mechanism and design of start interface.

gear wheel components (e.g. large-scale, small-scale, chain, and rechargeable components) provided by the game could generate power to drive the prepared scientific components based on the game operation of various assembly and arrangement. If a causality error occurred in the arrangement of the device, it might lead to the failure of chain reaction or inaccurate response results, and users had to think about arranging the appropriate assembly of power device.

To activate the power of gear wheels, it was necessary to establish “self-given power components” at a certain place of the game screen. In addition, there was a need to consider the solution procedure of the entire scenario script and to assess the level of difficulty for completing chain reaction. As shown in Figure 3, the power conveyance procedure included conveyance devices (power component A and B) and the tool modules (tools A, B, C, etc.) with specific functions. The analysis on the tool modules with specific function revealed that such tool modules were closely related to the start interface at the beginning of the starter device as defined by the scenario. For example, if the start interface was in tree shape, sawing off the branch could be viewed as the solution to the problem. Therefore, its trigger mechanism could be sawing-related tools. If users fulfilled their imagination and used unexpected tools, although it might not be a solution, it should be theoretically reasonable. This study intended to observe the learning process exhibited by users and how they arranged the assembly model of power components, rather than to explore which tool was used to complete the operation of start interface, during problem-solving. Therefore, the correlation between

motivate power mechanism and design of start interface should be explicitly and reasonably identified.

DESIGN THINKING ON CPS MODEL

This study further investigated the design thinking aspect that users should pay attention to during the process of imaging problem solving based on the concept analysis on chain reaction and investigation on design thinking of visual clues, including critical problems of scenario scripts, operational hints, and cognitive connection of start interface of tool modules. The assessment and analysis on the thinking of each operational stage based on the CPS concept proposed by Parnes were as follows:

FF TO PF STAGE: TO INVESTIGATE HOW USERS OBSERVED GAME SCREEN AND IDENTIFIED THE TYPES OF SCENARIO PROBLEMS

This stage was to observe how users identified and viewed the constitution of game screen, as well as the predetermined scenario problems. In terms of game design, game screen included the menu interface design as required by game process, device tools as required by operational process, power devices, and other components to assist in problem-solving. The chain reaction components of game scenarios, their arrangement, and animation reflecting plots would guide users in further operating and exploring games. Therefore, the hints of information contents would affect users’ operational effectiveness at this stage.

In terms of users’ awareness of scenario problems, four scenario structures guided users in exhibiting different problem-solving strategies and the ultimate purpose was to solve problems. For example, the

main purpose of Risk Precaution was to make players become aware of disasters and prevent them from occurring. In the game, the role successfully prevented a disaster from occurring based on the personal traits and creativity for problem-solving as the first person. The main purpose of Obstacle Eliminations was to enable players to solve the predicaments predetermined in the plots from the perspective of a third party, as well as to trigger their motivation based on observation and identification of predicaments. Situation Balances intended to trigger users' abstract perception for the concept of "inclination" from the perspective of the second/third person. In mathematical logic, "inclination" referred to proportion and was related to fair treatment in analog feeling. As long as the game operation was accurately completed, the imbalanced entire scenario would become balanced. Confident Challenges intended to trigger users' attitude of never giving up, being brave to give a try, and carrying through firmly to the end.

IF STAGE: TO UNDERSTAND HOW USERS THOUGHT ABOUT THE CORRELATION AMONG MOTIVATE POWER MECHANISM, TOOL TYPE OF COMPONENTS, AND CHAIN REACTION COMPONENTS

This stage was to further explore the functionality of component tools and if the chain reaction developed by the assembly of power components could correctly trigger the interface of chain reaction procedure after users understood scenario problems. The correlation among thinking power, component tool, and scenario problems could be analyzed based on three factors, "operational component," "operational action," and "operational result," as described in Figure 4.

"Operational components" referred to power components, such as gear wheels and conveyor belts, the components which could generate and convey power. The operational actions varied with the inherent mechanics of devices, and there were different operational results naturally. Although the operational actions for the components varied, they were still the assembly, arrangement, stacking, and juxtaposition of various components. The continuous procedures among components would trigger interesting chain reactions. "Operational actions" could be further investigated from the perspective of

Figure 4. Correlation among tool module operation, game operations, and scenario problems of chain reaction. (TM: Tool Module)

specific functions of operational components. They usually referred to the operational mechanism possessed by components themselves, such as the inherent mechanics mentioned above. The status of "operational results" could be reviewed as the results exhibited by object of target in the aspects of volume, space, and physics after operational actions occurred.

From the perspective of users' operational action, this stage mainly investigated how to choose and which component tool to apply to the establishment of chain reactions to trigger the interface of chain reaction components and conditions and to further achieve the purpose. The behavior conductor was described based on the behavioral relationship between people and objects, such as the behavioral/operational descriptions of people or objects, including "beating," "pressing," "pushing," "squeezing," "taking," "puncturing," "opening," and "rolling." These descriptions about behaviors were all extremely comprehensible, and the connection

Figure 5. Schematic diagram of the relationship between self-given power components, start interface, and response gap.

between behavior object and behavior conductor was not a single connection. For example, “balloons” were objects, and the behaviors such as “puncturing,” “beating,” and “taking” were all reasonable behavioral performance. It could be inferred that, when users thought about which chain reaction start interface should be used to conduct experiments on component tools, they would be affected by the level of clues and hints (e.g. the suggestibility of tool icon and operational behavior) apart from their own imagination, and thus exhibited different awareness and operational action for choosing tools.

SF TO AF STAGE: TO SUMMARIZE AND ASSESS THE POSSIBLE ASSEMBLY OF VARIOUS SOLUTIONS

This stage was to investigate how users operated component tools to assemble chain reactions, how they integrated power components to generate the initial power of chain reaction, and how they exhibited the ability to solve exploration problems during the operational process of the entire game. Figure 5 was the schematic diagram of relationship among self-given power components, start interface, and response gap. If the self-given power components provided by scenario problems were at a fixed location (such as area A) in the screen and the start interface of the chain reaction procedure was also fixed at a specific area (such as area B), the

users’ task was to establish the chain reaction procedure connecting A with B, and such a connection was completed by operating component tools and assembling power. However, if components and interface were not fixed at area A and area B, the results of component assembly would surely be uncertain. In addition, the difference in the original status of game rules would lead to dynamic change. Therefore, the users’ problem-solving ability and learning involved many variables and had to be further investigated.

In the process of the predetermined chain reaction, some chain reaction components would vary with their locations in the specific space, which made the original chain reaction procedure become invalid due to the change in rules. The response gap caused by it should be complemented by the assembly of other components. Therefore, users had to develop more problem-solving strategies during the game process. In general, users’ operation and components assembly further triggered chain reaction procedure, and the entire process could be viewed as the process of go-and-return among IF, SF, and AF stages. Users might preliminarily assess scenarios after they identified problems and obtained the basic solutions. When users further explored the problems, the feedback results, operational experiences, and cognitive responses generated during the process would also be amended to construct the

understanding of component tools and the entire chain reaction. Moreover, each exploration naturally reduced the assessment stage, which was similar to the behavior to amend operational direction due to heuristic trial and error (i.e. Heuristic operation). As a result, the integrity of game problems would be limited by image information presentation at this stage, which further affected users' application of imagination, analysis and assessment, and exhibition of various problem-solving abilities and models.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study investigated the interactive game design method and design thinking for the problem-solving based on the design concept of chain reaction components. This study developed the game scenario contents, game interface, and prototype of game interactive design. The game guided users in choosing accurate and appropriate trigger tools to establish the gear wheel components for continuous power. The game objective of problem-solving was further achieved by activating the chain reaction procedure composed of various scientific components. This study discussed the design thinking concept and visual design factor required by each stage of four scenario design based on the CPS model proposed by Parnes (1967).

The research results show that the hinting method of signal information influences the effects in the FF and PF stages, and the hinting level has a significant perceptive difference in terms of IF. In the SF and AF stages, completeness of the image information influences the breadth of the evaluation strategies. The research results hope to explore the cognitive processes in image-based problem-solving ability, and can assist the designers to consider the design of interactive games and strengthen problem-solving abilities.

Future studies will observe and record users' game operation by using thinking aloud method, content analysis, image record, and qualitative research to observe and analyze users' cognitive procedures and response at each stage of CPS model and to summarize game response, feedback, as well as the current status and response in the aspects of interface design, image design, and interactive design. It was hoped that the results could be provided as reference for image hints and clues to

guide users in developing various design thinking for problem-solving during operational process.

Acknowledgement: The author is very grateful to National Science Council (Taiwan, R. O. C.) for providing budget to accomplish this research project. (NSC99-2410-H-134-015-MY2)

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Appendix. Components design and functions description.

Name of components	Demonstrations	Functions description
Large-scale and small-scale gear wheel		<p>They are used to connect and convey power. The integration of large-scale with small-scale gear wheels was flexibly used to establish the connection with chain reaction. Power short-circuit failure should be avoided, and the number for use was not limited.</p>
Chain gear wheel		<p>Two large-scale gear wheels constituted a set of chain gear wheel component. Its function was to connect and convey power. The length of the chain was limited. If one of the two gear wheels was powered up, the other would rotate in the same direction because it would be driven by the chain. Power short-circuit failure should be avoided during usage.</p>
Rechargeable gear wheel		<p>Such gear wheels are capable of accumulating electricity and releasing power. General gear wheels will not function until they are connected with external power. However, after rechargeable gear wheels completed staged electricity storage (stage 00 to 10), it can still spontaneously release power until electricity was completely consumed even though it lost external power. At most two sets of rechargeable gear wheels could be used. For the use of two sets of gear wheels, it was necessary to set up two cycles for the overall electricity storage and power release to avoid the unlimited power conveyance.</p>
Finger tool kit		<p>Used for specific operational purpose. The force application angle could be arbitrarily adjusted. For the actions such as moving objects, touching, pushing, and pressing, a finger image was used as the hint. As the gear wheel tool kit generated power, fingers would move back and forth to complete the specific operational action.</p>

Name of components	Demonstrations	Functions description
Scissor tool kit		<p>Used for specific operational purpose. The operational angle could be arbitrarily adjusted. For actions such as cutting off lines, cutting off objects, and cutting objects, the continuously opened scissor image was used as a hint. As the gear wheel tool kit generates power, scissors would move back and forth and opened repeatedly to complete the specific operational action.</p>
Tapping tool kit		<p>Used for specific operational purpose. The force application direction could be arbitrarily adjusted. For actions such as knocking, beating, hitting, and pounding, the image of a hand holding a mallet was used as a hint. As the gear wheel tool kit generates power, mallet would move back and forth and presented the repeated knocking processing to complete the specific operational action.</p>
Air pressure tool kit		<p>Used for specific operational purpose. Operational direction could be arbitrarily adjusted. For the actions such as blowing, filling air, blowing up objects (balloon or gas bag), increasing pressure to emit object, the images of repeatedly expanded and contracted gas bag and narrow pressure pipeline were used as hints. As the gear wheel tool kit generates power, air pressure device would be fixed but the pressure would repeatedly increase or decrease to complete specific operational action.</p>

Name of components	Demonstrations	Functions description
Ignition tool kit		<p>Used for specific purpose. The operation direction could be arbitrarily adjusted. For the actions such as use of source for ignition (e.g. igniting gas stove and candles), the image of sporadic sparks cause by object friction was used as the hint. As the gear wheel tool kit generates power, the device would be stably fixed and the repeated generation of sparks caused by friction would complete specific operational action.</p>
Spray tool kit		<p>Used for specific operational purpose. The operational direction could be arbitrarily adjusted. For the actions such as spraying water, spurting water to put out a fire or watering. The tool could not release water until it stored water in advance. The image similar to injection tool was used as a hint. As the gear wheel tool kit generates power, the injector would have absorbed external water resource and the water storage device would operate. On the contrary, if the injector had not absorbed water, the spraying would be initiated to complete specific operational action.</p>